

A Fake-Authored COVID-19–Related Paper Continues to Rake In Citations: Broad Implications for the Medical Sciences

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Abstract

The medical sciences are under threat of fake research, and also fake authors. One of the downsides of the COVID-19 pandemic was the abuse of weaknesses of the publishing system to push through fake and fraudulent science. One such paper, by a fake author (“Alireza Heidari”), continues to accumulate citations, accruing 24 citations until 13 December 2025. Absent corrective measures, unscientific behavior will proliferate. Medical scientists need to appreciate that it is not easy to appreciate a fake from a real author, and that citation of work by fake authors will eventually infiltrate into the body of legitimate scientific knowledge, corrupting it.

Keywords: Editorial oversight; Fake; Integrity; Misinformation; Peer review; Post-publication peer review

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INTRODUCTION

This perspective abridges the issue of identity fakery, which may have an impact on the wider medical science community, drawing on a case that emerged at the height of the COVID-19 pandemic period.

In the initial days of the COVID-19 pandemic, seemingly almost anything and everything related to the SARS-CoV-2 virus was published, leading to an historically unprecedented volume of medical literature being published [1]. In several cases, due to excessive editorial enthusiasm, wanting to publish “hot” research on this theme, peer reviewers

and editors would occasionally cut corners of stringent quality control, resulting in the publication of fake as well as poorly vetted science that eventually needed to be retracted [2]. As with any global crisis, some entities took advantage of that global medical naivety and time of uncertainty to make mockery of the culture of the scientific, academic and publishing enterprise. While peer-reviewed literature occasionally failed to screen out pseudoscience, with preprints not faring much better, truly predatory or unscholarly publishing venues, which falsely claim peer review while not conducting it, also allowed the publication of some pseudoscience that may have been construed by unsuspecting eyes as being actual science. When COVID-19 was declared a pandemic, a warning was issued that academics need to be vigilant of fake scientific papers published in publishing venues that claimed falsely to publish valid medical literature [3].

In that editorial, particular note was made of a 39-page open access paper led by a fake identity “Alireza Heidari”¹, who has – through publication and citation of their own papers – polluted a vast expanse of literature, including on medical topics, both in potentially predatory and academically valid (peer-reviewed) publishing venues. There are at least four red flags associated with that paper. First, the initial term used in that paper, “Coronavirus nanoparticles”, is a non-existent and thus pseudoscientific construct. Second, the likely cheap-fake or deep-fake image of the lead author is accompanied by a well-known fake affiliation (California South University) as well as a hijacked one (American International Standards Institute). Third, the paper carries no methodology or logical structure, and is merely a collection of seemingly “scientific” terms all randomly strung together, accompanied by a series of images, some of them cloned from previous sources, but all bundled together to give the false impression of a “scientific paper”. Fourth, the paper is a massive self-citation plantation, in two forms: first, as dozens of random, meaningless papers claiming to support an individual claim; second, 386 citations in the reference list to “Heidari”, alone or with other members of the cheap-fake or deep-fake team. On that paper’s webpage, we learn that the paper, which was published in March 2020, has been viewed 25,042 times, the PDF has been downloaded 5512 times, and the XML has been downloaded 4364 times by 13 December 2025, i.e., a heavily viewed and downloaded paper.

Just under five years later (13 December 2025), that pseudoscience paper has already been cited 24 times, according to Google Scholar (Table 1). There are two striking aspects of that list of citations. The first are vast quantities of self-citations by “Heidari” to “Heidari”, an abusive practice because those citations do not offer valid support to the claims to which they are associated. This is a trademark across “Heidari” papers, and a fascinating scientific bibliometric phenomenon in itself. Secondly, and more worrisome, are that papers in two journals, typically considered to be published by non-predatory whitelisted and thus “safe-to-publish-in” status quo publishers, *Scientific Reports* and *PLOS ONE*, cited this “Heidari” et al. pseudoscience. Peer review and editorial oversight clearly failed at these two mega open access journals [4].

How does one curtail the citation of pseudoscience like the “Heidari” et al. paper? First, this requires embracing the truthful reality that fake elements are not only present in scientific publishing; rather, they are pervasive [5]. Second, pseudoscience is populating not only Google Scholar, but also established scientific databases or medical platforms like PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science. Third, there needs to be a firm recognition by the wider medical scientific community that the “Heidari” et al. paper is pseudoscience. Fourth, mainstream publishers like Springer Nature and PLOS, who publish *Scientific Reports* and *PLOS ONE*, respectively, need to accept the unfortunate reality that their publishing business model is failing some core value systems [6]. Finally, there is a need to track down and criminalize the creators

¹ <https://openaccesspub.org/jvat/article/1290> (Alireza Heidari, Angela Caissutti, Maria Henderson, Katrina Schmitt, Elizabeth Besana, Jennifer Esposito, Victoria Peterson (2020) Recent new results and achievements of California South University (CSU) BioSpectroscopy Core Research Laboratory for COVID-19 or 2019-nCoV treatment: diagnosis and treatment methodologies of “coronavirus”. *Journal of Current Viruses and Treatment Methodologies*, 1(1), 3-41. <https://doi.org/10.14302/issn.2691-8862.jvat-20-3275> (CC-BY license)

of deepfakes [7]. If these five points of advice are not heeded, there is a risk that the value and credibility of scientific collections claiming to be “peer-reviewed” may implode under the weight of an excessively heavy load of pseudoscience, gradually – with the accumulation of errors, retractions and citation of fake science – reverting such literature (and the journals they are published in) to a “junk” status [8]. By virtue of the dynamics by which academic papers are linked, via referencing, a crisis in science, in the form of the circulation of bad science and pseudoscience, will express itself exponentially through citations [9].

Finally, how should the medical academic community view and characterize those journals and publishers that reap citations and make profit off pseudoscience, often while hiding behind their ethical branding [10]?

Table 1. Summary of the 24 citations¹ to a fake COVID-19 pseudoscience paper authored by a team, led by a fake “author”.

DOI or URL	Journal / book chapter Publisher
https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31276-6	<i>Scientific Reports</i> Springer Nature
https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281981	<i>PLOS ONE</i> PLOS
https://doi.org/10.36348/sjbr.2020.v05i06.007	<i>Saudi Journal of Biomedical Research</i> Scholars Middle East Publishers
https://doi.org/10.36348/sjbr.2020.v05i06.008	<i>Saudi Journal of Biomedical Research</i> Scholars Middle East Publishers
https://doi.org/10.36348/sjbr.2020.v05i07.005	<i>Saudi Journal of Biomedical Research</i> Scholars Middle East Publishers
https://doi.org/10.36348/sjbr.2020.v05i07.004	<i>Saudi Journal of Biomedical Research</i> Scholars Middle East Publishers
https://doi.org/10.15761/DOMR.1000340	<i>Dental, Oral and Maxillofacial Research</i> Open Access Text
https://doi.org/10.15761/DOMR.1000337	<i>Dental, Oral and Maxillofacial Research</i> Open Access Text
https://doi.org/10.15761/DOMR.1000338	<i>Dental, Oral and Maxillofacial Research</i> Open Access Text
https://doi.org/10.15761/DOMR.1000339	<i>Dental, Oral and Maxillofacial Research</i> Open Access Text
https://doi.org/10.15761/DOMR.1000342	<i>Dental, Oral and Maxillofacial Research</i> Open Access Text
https://doi.org/10.15761/DOMR.1000343	<i>Dental, Oral and Maxillofacial Research</i> Open Access Text
https://doi.org/10.15761/DOMR.1000347	<i>Dental, Oral and Maxillofacial Research</i> Open Access Text
tiny.cc/PJSE24476153v7i10p077-115 ²	<i>Parana Journal of Science and Education</i> <i>Parana Journal of Science and Education</i>
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3880506	<i>Parana Journal of Science and Education</i>

https://dx.doi.org/10.21608/aujes.2020.124566	<i>Parana Journal of Science and Education</i> <i>Aswan University Journal of Environmental Studies</i> Aswan University
https://doi.org/10.30564/ssid.v1i2.1827	<i>Semiconductor Science and Information Devices</i> Bilingual Publishing Co.
https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8936-6.ch018	Book chapter IGI Global
https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-7640-9.ch010	Book chapter IGI Global
https://doi.org/10.12691/ijp-10-1-1 ^{3,4}	<i>International Journal of Physics</i> SciEP
https://doi.org/10.12691/jmpc-9-2-1	<i>Journal of Materials Physics and Chemistry</i> SciEP
https://openaccesspub.org/lung-cancer-epidemiology/article/1776 ⁴	<i>Journal of Lung Cancer Epidemiology</i> Open Access Pub

¹According to Google Scholar (search date: 13 December 2025):

https://scholar.google.co.jp/scholar?start=0&hl=en&as_sdt=2005&sciodt=0.5&cites=4667430612472322444&scipsc=

² A duplicate copy of this paper exists, published in 2022 (<https://openaccesspub.org/lung-cancer-epidemiology/article/1776>), but about 50 citations have been truncated, including to this paper.

³ Careful note should be made of the last and senior author, an apparent impersonation of a US TV host “Jimmy Kimmel” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jimmy_Kimmel).

⁴ These papers were not listed in the December 2025 Google Scholar search, but was discovered in the initial December 2024 Google Scholar search.

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